

1 A century of National Forest Inventory in 2 Norway – informing past, present, and 3 future decisions

4 Johannes Breidenbach *; Aksel Granhus; Gro Hysten; Rune Eriksen; Rasmus Astrup

5 National Forest Inventory, Norwegian Institute of Bioeconomy Research

6 * Correspondence: [first name].[last name]@nibio.no

7 1 Abstract

8 **Past:** In the early 20th century, forestry was one of the most important sectors in Norway and an
9 agitated discussion about the perceived decline of forest resources due to over-exploitation was
10 ongoing. To base the discussion on facts, the young state of Norway established
11 *Landsskogtakseringen* – the world’s first National Forest Inventory (NFI). Field work started in 1919
12 and was carried out by county. Trees were recorded on 10 m wide strips with 1-5 km interspace. Site
13 quality and land cover categories were recorded along each strip. Results for the first county were
14 published in 1920 and by 1930, most forests below the coniferous tree line were inventoried. The 2nd
15 to 5th inventories followed in the years 1937-1986. As of 1954, temporary sample plot clusters on a
16 3×3 km grid were used as sampling units.

17 **Present:** The current NFI grid was implemented in the 6th NFI from 1986 to 1993, where permanent
18 plots on a 3×3 km grid were established below the coniferous tree line. As of the 7th inventory in
19 1994, the NFI is continuous, and 1/5th of the plots are measured annually. All trees with a diameter
20 ≥5 cm are recorded on circular, 250 m² plots. The NFI grid was expanded in 2005 to cover alpine
21 regions with 3×9 and 9×9 km grids. In 2012, the NFI grid within forest reserves was doubled along
22 the cardinal directions. Clustered temporary plots are used periodically to facilitate county-level
23 estimates. As of today, more than 120 variables are recorded in the NFI including bilberry cover,
24 drainage status, deadwood, and forest health. Land-use changes are monitored and trees outside
25 forests are recorded.

26 **Future:** Considerable research efforts towards the integration of remote sensing technologies enable
27 the publication of the Norwegian Forest Resource Map since 2015, which is also used for small area
28 estimation on the municipality level. On the analysis side, capacity and software for long term
29 growth and yield prognosis are maturing. Furthermore, we foresee the inclusion of further variables
30 for monitoring ecosystem services, and an increasing demand for mapped information. The
31 relatively simple NFI design has proven to be a robust choice for satisfying steadily increasing
32 information needs and concurrently providing consistent time series.

33 2 Introduction

34 Statistics on forest resources and their future development are pivotal to make informed decisions
35 in times of a changing environment. In most of the developed world, we today take for granted to
36 have this form of information provided by National Forest Inventories (NFIs) (Tomppo et al. 2010,
37 Vidal et al. 2016). Indeed, governments were only willing to bear the huge costs and ongoing
38 commitment of an NFI system because the lack of reliable statistics on forest resources became
39 untenable. The first NFIs were implemented in the Nordic countries due to a fear of
40 overexploitations of the forest resource. Norway started with institutional settings and planning in
41 1917, and field-work in 1919 (Landsskogtakseringen 1920), while Finland and Sweden followed in
42 the early 1920s (Ilvessalo 1927, Thorell and Ostlin 1931, Kangas et al. 2018). The USA implemented a
43 forest monitoring program in the late 1920s. The fear of forest decline due to acid rain in the 1980s
44 was among the reasons for the implementation of NFIs in western Germany - despite the availability
45 of detailed local forest management inventories (Kleinn et al. 2020 in press). Information
46 requirements resulting from mitigation of climate change (REDD+) but also incentives in the form of
47 development aid resulted in establishing NFIs in developing countries since around 2000 (e.g.
48 Tomppo et al. 2014).

49 The main motivation of the first NFIs was to provide statistics on the main dendrometrical variables
50 such as timber volume and volume increment, to guide political decisions that guaranteed a
51 sustainable management of the timber resource. Today, NFIs have gradually developed to include
52 many other ecosystem services and often are landscape inventories covering the land-based
53 resources of a country. The Norwegian NFI, as many others, is for example used to estimate the
54 areas and changes among the land use categories like forest, grassland, croplands, wetlands, and
55 settlements that are required for reporting under the Climate Convention (UN 1992). However,
56 already the first Norwegian NFI mapped other land resources than forest such as grassland,
57 cropland, and mires. The clear aim of this setup was to support decisions on afforestation activities
58 for example by the drainage of mires. In subsequent inventories, the description of the production
59 potential of existing forest was made to support decisions on how low-productive forests could be
60 replaced with forests consisting of more productive tree species. To provide useful information,
61 estimates had to be reliable for rather small administrative units. Until recently, Norway was split
62 into 20 administrative regions referred to as counties. All historic Norwegian NFIs until the 1990s
63 had sample designs that allowed reliable estimates at least on the level of these counties. Later,
64 additional data have been collected on temporary plots to periodically provide county-level
65 information. The second Norwegian NFI even provided reliable estimates for municipalities which,
66 besides the war times, was the reason for the long duration from 1937-1956. Municipal-level
67 inventories based on sample plots additional to the national grid were common until the mid-1980s
68 (Tomter 2019, p. 186).

69 While the provision of small-scale estimates was less in the focus of the Norwegian NFIs towards the
70 end of the 20th century, the lack of this information was one of the main reasons for developing the
71 forest resource map SR16 which is based on a combination of NFI field plots and 3D remotely sensed
72 data (Astrup et al. 2019). SR16 provides maps of the main forest characteristics such as biomass,
73 timber volume, and tree species on 16x16 m² rasters and is used for small area estimates on
74 municipal level (Breidenbach and Astrup 2012). When overseeing a long NFI history, also the
75 repetition of other questions become visible, albeit in a new context to address present-time
76 challenges. For example, NFI data were recently used to estimate the climate mitigation potential of
77 replacing low-productive unmanaged deciduous forests with more productive coniferous forest
78 (Bright et al. 2020, submitted). While this topic was of great interest in the 1920s because of the aim
79 to increase timber production, it is today again under discussion in Norway as one option to increase
80 the CO₂ uptake of forests. Another example is the implementation of sampling designs that allow
81 annual estimates which was already implemented in the fourth NFI from 1964-1976. This design
82 marks a stronger emphasis on national estimates than on local to regional estimates. Since the mid-

83 1990s, this concept is used again when the NFI became a continuous program, which was needed for
84 the annual reporting to Statistics Norway. The continuous system also has other advantages like
85 maintaining the knowledge within the NFI team.

86 The technological and societal changes over the last 100 years in Norway naturally coined the
87 development of the NFI. The increasing availability of topographical maps, albeit coarse by today's
88 standards, determined the order in which counties were inventoried in the first NFI. Strip sampling
89 was the most cost-effective way to gain information because of lacking infrastructure and modern
90 forms of (air-) transportation (Kleinn and Tomter 1993). Sample plots were used after World War II,
91 when the forest road network expanded rapidly, and motorized transportation became the
92 standard. The development of inventory techniques was utilized to make the field data collection
93 more efficient over time. Besides fixed sample plots, also concentric sample plots and angle count
94 sampling (ACS) (Bitterlich 1948) were utilized throughout the years. Today, elements of fixed sample
95 plots, concentric sample plots, ACS, cluster sampling, and line intersect sampling are utilized to
96 assess the various variables. The technological development of motorized transportation, satellite-
97 based navigation, emergency localization, mobile communication, hand-held computers, and ultra-
98 sound measurement devices resulted in the gradual reduction of field teams from 6-9 persons in the
99 first NFI to just one since around 2000.

100 The increased information requirements of modern societies are also reflected in the Norwegian
101 NFI. The number of recorded items has increased over the years to more than 120 tree-, stand-, and
102 landscape-level variables. The creators of the first NFI certainly would be excited to hear that the NFI
103 today also fulfills governmental reporting duties under various international treaties such as the
104 global Forest Resource Assessment (MacDicken 2015) or the Climate Convention. The reporting
105 requirements of the latter also resulted in a design change as from 2005. Then, also the forest in
106 low-productive alpine regions, typically dominated by mountain birch (*Betula pubescens ssp.*
107 *czerepanovii*), were included in the sampling frame and the NFI today covers the whole Norwegian
108 land area. The currently implemented design proved to be robust for the required adjustments so
109 far.

110 Besides the generation of forest statistics, the Norwegian NFI has also been an important base for
111 research. More than 60 scientific articles using NFI data have been published until today – the
112 majority of them after 2000 (Tomter 2019, p. 170). Topics of those studies were among others the
113 improvement of inventory methodology, biological models, and forest sector prognosis. Early
114 research was seldomly internationally published. For example, Alf Langsæter, one of the first NFI
115 analysts, published several scientific reports in Norwegian (e.g. Langsaeter 1932, Langsaeter 1934).
116 Among them was a work on uncertainty estimation in systematic strip sampling (Langsæter 1926)
117 which contained early descriptions of estimators that are still studied today (Magnussen et al. 2020).

118 The role of international cooperation was of great importance for the development of the
119 Norwegian NFI. The first NFI report highlights the knowledge exchange with and influence of the
120 Swedish NFI on the chosen sampling design (Landsskogtakseringen 1933, p.6). The exchange with
121 the Nordic countries was, and still is, significant (Kangas et al. 2018). Also the cooperation through
122 the European National Forest Inventory Network (ENFIN) and beyond has been an important source
123 of inspiration and quality assurance for the recent Norwegian NFIs (Tomppo et al. 2010).

124 The first Norwegian NFI showed that increment and harvest were approximately in balance (Figure
125 1). This calmed down the discussions regarding the fear of over-exploitations of the forest resource
126 (Barth 1916). The NFI documents an increase of the growing stock timber volume by a factor of
127 three over the last 100 years (Figure 1). Many policy decisions, often informed by NFI statistics, had
128 an influence on this result. Among them were the change of the silviculture system to even-aged
129 stand management with active reforestation after harvests, afforestation, breeding of improved
130 seed material, and institutionalized research and education. One of the main drivers for this

131 development was, however, the substitution of wood as the primary energy source by fossil fuels. In
 132 the recent decades (Figure 1), the feed-back effects of the large fossil fuel combustion are becoming
 133 visible in an increased increment attributed among others to increased N-deposition (Solberg et al.
 134 2004) and longer growing seasons due to climate change (Nordli et al. 2008). The fundamental
 135 societal changes required to form a fossil-free bioeconomy without the loss of today's welfare will
 136 require dramatic policy decisions. We are therefore confident that data provided by NFIs will be of
 137 high importance also in the future.

138
 139 *Figure 1: Growing stock volume under bark, annual increment and fellings for the period 1919–2017. Standard errors for*
 140 *volume and increment are in the order of 1% and 2%, respectively. Fellings are based on a census survey by Statistics*
 141 *Norway.*

142
 143 Despite its long history, only few international accounts of the Norwegian NFI system have been
 144 published (Landsskogtakseringen 1968, Kleinn and Tomter 1993, Tomter et al. 2010, Tomter 2016).
 145 Our aim is therefore to describe developments in the past, present, and foreseeable future design
 146 and use of the Norwegian NFI. By sharing experiences gained throughout the years, we hope to
 147 contribute to the ongoing development of the Norwegian NFI and the NFIs around the globe. In the
 148 remainder of the text, we will use the acronym NFI to refer to the Norwegian National Forest
 149 Inventory, unless otherwise specified.

150 3 The historical development of the NFI

151 3.1 Historical background

152 The description of the historical background is based on books in Norwegian that were published to
 153 celebrate anniversaries of the NFI and the organizations hosting the NFI at the time
 154 (Landsskogtakseringen 1970, Strand 1994, Øyen 2006, Tomter 2019). The reports of the early NFIs
 155 were valuable resources regarding the applied methodology (Landsskogtakseringen 1920,
 156 Landsskogtakseringen 1933).

157 Reports on local overexploitation of forests date back to the 17th century when also the first laws
 158 regulating timber export and the establishment of saw mills were enacted. Besides the still typical
 159 use of timber for construction, huge amounts of firewood were required in households and the dairy

160 production on alpine summer farms in many regions. Domestic animals foraging near the summer
161 farms also led to local forest degradation and even a lowering of the tree line compared to the
162 current-day level (Bryn and Daugstad 2001, Bryn and Potthoff 2018). Charcoal was the primary
163 energy source in Norway's early industry and was used in mining and processing of iron, copper, and
164 silver.

165 Aiming at protecting the regeneration of forests, high-grading was enforced as the forest
166 management regime, where the harvest of trees below a certain diameter was strongly forbidden.
167 Due to the high timber demand, the fastest growing trees had a high likelihood to be harvested first,
168 which over time contributed to a slower growth of the forests. High-grading was still the prevailing
169 management regime when Agnar Barth (1916) published an influential article where he predicted
170 the doom of the Norwegian forest. It included a back-of-the envelope estimate according to which
171 the harvest levels were 29% higher than the increment.

172 Initial ideas of obtaining national forest statistics date back to 1737, when Norway's first forest
173 administration was founded. The commitment of the king that ruled Denmark-Norway from the
174 Danish capital Copenhagen was, however, not strong enough to implement such a revolutionary
175 task. During the 19th century, a growing population together with the release of sawmilling privileges
176 in the 1840s and a growing pulpwood industry, increased the timber demand and led to local timber
177 shortage. The increasing utilization of the forest resources generally took place without knowledge
178 on whether the harvest was sustainable, although some attempts were made to estimate volume
179 increment and removals (Skogkommisjonen 1874, Helland 1894). The problem of those estimates
180 was that they were not authoritative because uncertainties remained unknown and the need of
181 better forest statistics was repeatedly formulated by the forest administration.

182 While it is unknown since when local forest management inventories have been conducted in
183 Norway, a case from the municipality Åmot in 1907 is documented. The inventory was started by
184 using 0.1 ha sample plots that were subjectively located in representative stands. By 1909, the
185 design was changed to strip sampling to finalize the inventory of the northern part of the
186 municipality. At a meeting of the Swedish Forestry Association in 1909 on methods of obtaining
187 information on volume and increment in all of Sweden's forests, participants of the forest inventory
188 in Åmot reported from their experiences. Swedish representatives also visited Åmot around that
189 time. Using strip sampling, they conducted an inventory of Värmland county in 1911-1912 as a pilot
190 study for the whole of Sweden (Anon. 1914).

191 The Norwegian State Forest Inventory (SFI) had the duty to conduct forest management inventories
192 of the forests owned by the Norwegian state and started using strip sampling around 1914. When
193 the director of Statistics Norway, Nicolay Rygg, met with experts of the SFI in 1915, he had since
194 several years plans to get more reliable information on the Norwegian forest resources. At the
195 meeting, Rygg got to know about the inventory of Värmland in Sweden and the experiences of the
196 SFI gained in Norway. Together with experts from the SFI, he developed a preliminary plan for an NFI
197 in Norway which he brought forward to the prime minister Gunnar Knudsen. The positive response
198 of the prime minister resulted in funds to elaborate a plan and budget of an NFI as a governmental
199 institution which was accepted by a parliament decision 13 June 1917.

200 3.2 The first NFI

201 The NFI was formally established 1 June 1919, when a leader and assistant were employed that were
202 responsible for conducting the first NFI. They were supported by a commission consisting of three
203 inventory experts. Right after his employment in June 1919, the leader of the NFI visited the Swedish
204 forest research institute to study the Värmland inventory in detail which had a big influence on the
205 NFI design. Field work started in August 1919 in Østfold county and carried on by county until field
206 work was finalized in 1930, while the first county-level reports were published much earlier (e.g.
207 Landsskogtakseringen 1920). All counties were fully covered except for western and northern

208 Norway. As can be seen from Figure 2, only large contiguous areas with forest were included in
 209 western Norway due to the low forest cover in large parts of that area. The two northernmost
 210 counties Finnmark and Troms and an area around Rendalen in eastern Norway were not covered by
 211 the NFI because most of these regions were state-owned and had been inventoried by the SFI
 212 (Landsskogtakseringen 1933, p. 28). As for all following NFIs until 2005, the surveyed population was
 213 the area below the coniferous forest limit.

214
 215 *Figure 2: Maps of southern and northern Norway showing the coverage and strip density of the first NFI (source:*
 216 *Landsskogtakseringen 1933). Numbers: Inventory areas (counties). Red lines: Inventory strips.*

217 3.2.1 Field measurements

218 Field work was carried out along 10 m wide strips that were oriented perpendicular to the main
 219 valleys in the respective county or watershed (Figure 2). The distance between the strips was
 220 between 1 and 5 km. Each strip was split into 2 km long segments that were treated as a 2 ha
 221 sampling unit. Within forest, the number of trees ≥ 15 cm dbh within 5 cm classes and the tree
 222 species groups spruce, pine, and deciduous were recorded. On the right half of the strip, also trees
 223 ≥ 5 cm were recorded. Trees between 0-5 cm were recorded on the right half of the strip for the
 224 eastern-most 100 m of every kilometer.

225 Sample trees were selected according to proportions that were determined before-hand by the
 226 headquarter. The proportions varied per county and diameter class. For the smallest trees, every
 227 50th to 300th tree was selected while every 3rd to 10th tree with a dbh ≥ 45 cm was selected. Tree
 228 species, distance to the center line, dbh in mm, diameter in 5 m, height, form height, damages, the
 229 latest 10-year's height growth, the latest 10-year's dbh growth, and age were recorded for sample
 230 trees. The increment cores taken for the latter two variables were collected for laboratory analysis.

231 An assessment of the site index (SI) was made by dividing the strip segments within forest into
 232 classes of high, medium and low productivity. In addition, the class protection forest, mostly towards
 233 the alpine border, described sensible forests that would become non-forest if too strongly
 234 harvested. Areas below the tree line were classified as productive forests, agriculture, extensive
 235 grasslands, forest pastures, mires, water, settlements, and barren land due to unfavorable growth
 236 conditions. Mires were categorized according to their suitability for drainage and all land was

237 categorized according to the possibility for converting it into cropland. The classification was largely
238 based on expert judgement.

239 The field teams consisted usually of at least six people: a team leader, a writing clerk, a navigator,
240 two men doing measurements and keeping the strip width, and one man doing the sample tree
241 measurements. While the team leader had to have a higher forestry education, the other team
242 members usually had college or high school education with a forestry major. At the end of each
243 week, which consisted of at least 48 working hours, the completed forms of each segment and a
244 report with a description of the progress and a place where the field crew could be found, were sent
245 by mail to the headquarters.

246 3.2.2 Office work

247 Sample tree volumes without bark were predicted by multiplying the tree's basal area with its height
248 and form factor (Landsskogtakseringen 1933, p. 30). The form factor method by Tor Jonson was
249 obviously very common at the time and therefore not further documented but most likely refers to
250 Johnson (1910). Volume and increment with bark were predicted using Swedish volume tables by
251 Tor Jonson (most likely: Jonson 1915). Mean-tree volume and increment were estimated for each
252 dbh class in the whole county. The number of trees was estimated by multiplying the recorded tree
253 numbers with the sampling fraction of the strips. The estimated number of trees was multiplied with
254 the middle tree volume and volume increment resulting from the sample trees to estimate total
255 volume and increment.

256 Parallel to the NFI, a Census Survey of Forest owners (CSF, *Skogbrukstelingen*) was conducted by
257 Statistics Norway 1920-1927, which provided information on harvest removals and forest-ownership
258 structure. The results of the first NFI and CSF showed that, over all, there was a balance between
259 increment and harvests. Data from the NFI, SFI, and CSF were combined for a complete assessment
260 of Norway's forests. The difference compared to earlier attempts to obtaining forest statistics was
261 that uncertainty could be estimated. Following the example of the Swedish inventory of Värmland,
262 simple random sampling within each of 10 groups of 2 km segments was assumed for variance
263 estimation in the beginning. The variance estimates of the 10 groups were then added to obtain a
264 variance for the whole area (Landsskogtakseringen 1920, p.89). Difference estimators developed by
265 Langsæter (1926) and his Nordic colleagues (Lindeberg 1924, Näslund 1930), were utilized for the
266 national estimates (Landsskogtakseringen 1933, p. 112). The standard errors for national forest area,
267 growing stock volume, and increment were 0.48%, 0.74%, and 0.77%, respectively.

268 3.3 The following NFIs until the 1990s

269 The second NFI in 1937-1956 aimed at providing reliable estimates for municipalities or groups of
270 municipalities. Strip sampling was used until 1956 with varying strip interspaces as small as 600 m.
271 As of 1956, temporary circular sample plots with an area of 78 m² were used that were laid out on
272 grids of 2-3 km × 200 m. In one county, a 3 km × 3 km grid was used with clusters of 20 plots at each
273 point. A more objective site index system with five categories and maturity classes (Section 5.3.2)
274 were introduced. Finnmark county, the northern-most part of Norway, was not included in the NFI
275 until 2005.

276 The third NFI in 1957-1964 aimed for relatively quickly providing updated information for larger
277 regions on the background of new fears of overexploitation of Norwegian forests after World War II.
278 For most part of the country, square clusters of 20 plots on a 3 km × 3 km grid were used. The
279 distance among plots in a cluster was 200 m and the circular plot area was 100 m². Several new
280 variables were recorded, among them stand type with respect to tree species mix, vegetation type,
281 terrain properties of interest for timber harvest, and soil type and depth.

282 The fourth NFI in 1964-1976 used the same design as before with the difference, that the clusters
283 were not measured per county. Instead, each year 1/12th of the clusters distributed over the whole

284 country were measured to provide national estimates quickly. Western Norway (and Finnmark) were
285 not covered by the NFI.

286 The fifth NFI in 1980-1986 was mostly based on clusters of 12-16 ACS plots. The counties in western
287 Norway were included with clusters mostly on a 3 km × 3 km grid. The smallest estimation unit for
288 the area that was covered by the last NFI were regions consisting of 2-3 counties where the grid size
289 varied between 4.8 km × 3.2 km and 7.2 km × 6.4 km. In that time, the NFI conducted various
290 municipal-level inventories by increasing the plot density locally.

291 The sixth NFI in 1986-1993 established permanent sample plots on a 3 km × 3 km grid below the
292 coniferous forest limit that are still used today. Clustered with each permanent plot were 3-11
293 temporary sample plots in distances of 250-500 m for county-level estimates (Section 6.1). On the
294 concentric sample plots, trees with a dbh ≥5 cm were measured on a 100 m² plot, while trees with a
295 dbh ≥20 cm were measured on a 200 m² plot. As of 1988, all data were recorded in field computers
296 instead of on paper.

297 3.3.1 Forest damage monitoring

298 Since 1984 a tree-crown condition survey was performed on all sample trees in the NFI due to
299 alarming reports of “novel forest damages” in central Europe (ICP Forest 2016). As of 1988, a variety
300 of crown condition variables were assessed annually on a subset of NFI plots located on a
301 9 km x 9 km grid for Norway spruce and Scots pine, and on a 18 km x 18 km grid for birch (Aamlid et
302 al. 2000). A soil survey was carried out for these plots 1988-1992 (Esser and Nyborg 1992, Esser
303 1994) which included a description of a representative soil profile and a soil sample for chemical
304 analysis. A sub-sample of plots was resampled after 5-6 years (Esser 1996). As of 2013, annual
305 assessments were stopped, and the crown condition survey was fully integrated in the 5-year NFI
306 cycle.

307 4 Institutional settings throughout time

308 For more than 50 years, the NFI was an independent institute answering directly to the Ministry of
309 Agriculture, with headquarters in Oslo. In December 1972, the NFI became a branch of the
310 Norwegian Forest Research Institute (NISK), and remained so until January 1988, when the tasks and
311 staff were transferred to the Norwegian Institute of Land Inventory (NIJOS), which was established
312 at the same time. In 2006, the forest research and land inventory institutes were merged to form the
313 Norwegian Forest and Landscape Institute, and the NFI was organized as a section within the new
314 institute. Since July 2015, the NFI has been organized as a Department within the Norwegian
315 Institute of Bioeconomy Research (NIBIO), which was formed after a merger of the Forest and
316 Landscape Institute with two other institutes that year. The Norwegian NFI is one of very few in
317 Europe that is not anchored in a national law (Polley 2020). Since 2019, the field staff of the NFI are
318 permanently employed in 24 full- or part-time positions. Previously, most of the field staff were
319 temporarily hired for the field season.

320 5 The present NFI system

321 5.1 The sample design

322 Since the 7th inventory in 1994, the NFI is continuous, and 1/5th of the plots are measured annually in
323 an inter-penetrating panel design. Due to the information requirements by the greenhouse gas
324 reporting, the NFI grid was expanded in 2005 to cover the alpine region (above the coniferous tree
325 line). For the same reason, the northernmost county Finnmark was for the first time included since
326 2005. Since the last sample plots in Finnmark were established in 2011, the sampled population is all
327 of Norway’s mainland area including lakes. The annually updated field manual has more than 200
328 pages (e.g. Viken 2018) and is the most detailed reference of the methods used in the NFI. Here, we
329 only describe a selection of the used methods and registered variables.

330 The permanent sample grid over all land use classes that is used for national estimates consists of
331 22,008 plots. The annual panel (i.e. 1/5th of the plots) is checked on the background of aerial images
332 in the office. If a plot is assumed to contain trees, or if it was previously registered in the field, field
333 staff is sent to the plot to make measurements. This includes plots that do not meet the forest
334 definition. To reduce the influence of topography, Norway is tessellated into Latin squares. Each
335 Latin square consists of 5x5=25 blocks, each with an area of 45 km (Viken 2018, p. 9). Each block
336 contains 9 plot locations on the 3x3 km grid to reduce traveling time. The panel of one year consists
337 of the plot locations within one block of each row of the Latin square. The Latin square design
338 assures no adjacent blocks are within the panel of plots of one year.

339 5.1.1 Design-strata

340 Stratification is often used to sample more observations on a denser sampling grid in potentially
341 productive areas, than in low-productive areas. In the NFI, a denser sampling grid is used in regions
342 where conifers can be of economic interest. The northernmost county of Finnmark was not included
343 in the NFI before 2005. Therefore, four design strata are utilized in the NFI; two in the northern-most
344 county of Finnmark (approximately east of 22° eastern longitude), and two outside Finnmark that
345 cover most of Norway's area (Figure 3). For simplicity, we will refer to the latter as being located
346 south of Finnmark. The sampling grid in the area south of Finnmark has a size of 3 km × 3 km in the
347 lowland region (stratum 1) and 3 km × 9 km in the low-productive alpine region (stratum 2). In the
348 latter, coniferous trees and active forest management seldomly occur (Table 1).

349 Stratum 1 covers approximately 46% of Norway's land area and more than 80% of the country's
350 forest. In Finnmark, a 3 km × 3 km grid is used within regions where coniferous trees, which in
351 Finnmark is mainly Scots pine, can form stands of economic interest (stratum 3) and a 9 km × 9 km
352 grid is used outside these regions (stratum 4). As opposed to the rest of the country, the coniferous
353 region is not mainly determined by elevation but by local topography. Norway spruce occurs
354 seldomly in Finnmark. While spruce, pine, and deciduous forests cover approximately equal parts in
355 stratum 1, almost 95% of the forests in stratum 4 are dominated by deciduous trees. The forest
356 proportion in the different strata ranges from 9.5% to 80.0% of which up to 0.8% are unstocked
357 areas (i.e. regeneration areas). Although the two coniferous tree species Norway spruce and Scots
358 pine stand for the majority of biomass in Norway (42% and 30%), deciduous trees (especially birches
359 *Betula pubescens* Ehrh. and *B. pendula* Roth.) dominate the majority (42%) of the forest area (Table
360 1). Because the sampling fraction differs among the strata, the plots represent different portions of
361 Norway's land area (sampling weights). The sampling weights for plots in strata 1-4 are
362 approximately 9 km², 27 km², 9 km², and 45 km².

363 While the Finnmark strata 3 and 4 are based on a map of productive and non-productive forest, the
364 decision on whether a plot belongs to stratum 1 or 2 was taken differently. For the municipalities
365 along the west-coast and northern Norway (north of the arctic circle), areas above a certain
366 elevation threshold were defined as alpine. These thresholds range from 100 m to 800 m a.s.l. and
367 were defined in cooperation with the local forest administration. Many municipalities in southern
368 and south-eastern Norway do not contain high mountains. For the remaining area (approximately
369 40% of the country), the stratum allocation was made by the field staff that visited each sample plot
370 on a 3 km × 3 km grid. If a plot showed characteristics of the alpine zone, this was recorded, and the
371 plot was only included in the sample, if it aligned with the 3 km × 9 km grid. For this area, a stratum
372 map based on universal Kriging using logit-transformed elevation as the covariable was created to
373 utilize remotely-sensed data in estimates. A spherical variogram model used to this end had a zero
374 nugget, a range of 5600 m and a sill of 0.73. The model was used to interpolate among the full 3 km
375 × 3 km grid with stratum information at each plot to create a 16 m x 16 m resolution map aligning
376 with the forest resource map SR16 (Astrup et al. 2019).

377 *Table 1: Forest area by dominating tree species group in the four NFI strata and all of Norway based on the NFI cycle from*
 378 *2014-2018.*

Stratum	Spruce (%)	Pine (%)	Deciduous (%)	Unstocked (%)	Area (km ²)	Forest (%)	# plots in forest	Forest area (km ²)
1	34.0	33.7	31.8	0.6	149,885	66.4	11,046	99,551
2	3.6	8.1	87.8	0.5	125,281	9.5	442	11,906
3	0.0	64.2	35.8	0.0	1,350	80.0	120	1,080
4	0.0	4.2	94.9	0.8	47,266	20.5	118	9,683
Norway	28.0	29.1	42.3	0.6	323,782	37.7	11,726	122,220

379

380

381

382 *Figure 3: NFI stratum map (aggregated to large hexagons for display purposes).*

383

384 5.2 Field measurements

385 Different sampling units are used to record the various variables in the field (Figure 4):

- 386 • Variables based on tree-level measurements such as growing stock volume, biomass, or
 387 increment are recorded on circular 250 m² plots (8.92 m radius) (Figure 4A). The plot center
 388 is marked with a metal stick buried in the ground and the center coordinate is measured
 389 using a handheld GPS. In addition, for 74% of the sample plots in forest so far, the

390 coordinates have been measured using survey-grade GPS equipment in an effort to measure
391 all center coordinates within the next years. If the sample plot center is located close to a
392 stand border, the plot is split into a maximum of two parts, if the stands are different with
393 respect to growing stock volume, maturity class (Section 5.3.2) or site index. Plots are also
394 split if one part covers a different land-use category. In any case, the smaller plot part must
395 have an area of at least 37.5 m² (15% of the total plot area) to split a plot. Assessments of
396 variables are carried out for each plot part. In addition to the tree-level measurements,
397 some other variables like the dominating vegetation type and soil depth are assessed using
398 the 250 m² plot as the basic registration unit.

- 399 • Stand- and landscape-level variables such as forest type (dominant tree species), stand age,
400 site index, maturity class (Section 5.3.2), soil type (mineral or organic), and land-use category
401 are recorded on 0.1 ha circular plots concentric with the plot center (Figure 4A). If the
402 250 m² plot is split, variables are assessed on two circle-segments, maintaining the
403 assessment area for each plot part at 0.1 ha by adjusting the radius of the circle segments
404 correspondingly.
- 405 • Biodiversity key habitats are recorded on a 2000 m² circle concentric to the center
406 coordinate (Figure 4A).
- 407 • In young forests (maturity classes 1 and 2), regeneration is assessed on five 16 m² circular
408 sample plots (2.26 m radius) located concentric with the plot center and 12 m in the cardinal
409 directions from the plot center (Figure 4B). Among others, species, and the number of trees
410 >30cm are recorded.
- 411 • Small trees (dbh ≤5 cm) are assessed on circular 5.3 m² plots (1.3 m radius) located 5 m from
412 the plot center in the cardinal directions. Tree species, the number of trees in two diameter
413 classes, and browsing damages are recorded (Figure 4C).
- 414 • The ericaceous shrubs bilberry (*Vaccinium myrtillus* L.) and lingonberry (*Vaccinium vitis-*
415 *idaea* L.) are important food sources for wild animals and as resources for berry picking.
416 Their coverage is recorded on 0.25 m² squares located 5 m from the plot center in the
417 cardinal directions (Figure 4C).
- 418 • Downed deadwood is assessed along two 18 m long east-west and north-south oriented
419 transects through the plot center (Figure 4D).
- 420 • The number of moose (*Alces alces* L.) and deer (*Cervus elaphus* L.) dropping patches are
421 recorded on a 100 m² plot concentric with the plot center (Figure 4D).

422 As of today, more than 120 variables are recorded in the NFI including bilberry cover, drainage
423 status, deadwood, stem rut, and forest health. In the following sections we will describe some of the
424 sampling units in more detail.

425

426 *Figure 4: Design of the permanent plots. A) Dendrometric variables for individual trees are measured on a plot sized 250 m²,
 427 here indicated in grey, while landscape- and stand-level variables, and key habitats are recorded on larger plots of 0.1 and
 428 0.2 ha, respectively. B) Tree densities and tree heights in young stands are measured on five subplots with radius 2.26 m
 429 (dotted circles). C) Four subplots are used to assess cover of bilberry and lingonberry (black squares), and for recording the
 430 number of trees with DBH <5 cm and browsing intensity (dotted circles). D) Patches of droppings from moose and deer is
 431 counted on a plot sized 100 m² (dark grey), while downed deadwood is measured along perpendicular transects of length
 432 18 m, here illustrated by the thick dotted lines.*

433 5.2.1 Tree-level measurements at the 250 m² plot

434 Diameter at breast height (dbh), tree species, and polar coordinates are recorded for all trees with a
 435 dbh ≥ 5 cm. Predictions of volume, biomass, and increment for these trees are utilized in the national
 436 estimates of these variables. A caliper with the scale pointing to the plot center is used to measure
 437 dbh. At 1.3 m height, a (discrete) mark of red spray paint is applied such that subsequent
 438 measurements can be done at the same height. Experience from plots close to hiking trails shows
 439 that the marks are only visible to those that know they exist. The measured dbh is manually
 440 recorded in the field computer which selects a subsample of height-measurement trees, denoted h-
 441 trees.

442 Tree heights are measured for a subsample of approximately 10 trees per plot (h-trees) using Vertex
 443 III (Haglöf 2002) devices. To obtain the subsample, an angle gauge factor determined by the previous
 444 measurement, is used. In case of large changes or a new establishment of a plot, the basal area is
 445 determined using ACS before calipering trees. If 10 or fewer trees are within the plot radius, the
 446 heights of all trees are measured. The decision to measure 10 h-trees was made in 2005 (previous to
 447 that, three h-trees were measured), to provide better reference data for remote sensing
 448 applications. For the same reason, survey grade GPS measurements of the plot coordinates are
 449 carried out by specialized field teams that do not measure other variables.

450 5.2.1.1 Prediction of volume and height

451 For each tree recorded on the 250 m² plot, a height is first approximated using tree h-dbh functions
 452 (Vestjordet 1968, Fitje and Vestjordet 1978, Eid and Fitje 1993). Using dbh and the approximated
 453 height, volumes are predicted using allometric functions (Braastad 1966, Brantseg 1967, Vestjordet

1967, Bauger 1995). Volume functions for Norway spruce (Vestjordet 1967) are used for all spruce and fir species except for Sitka spruce (*Picea sitchensis* (Bong.) Carr.) where a separate function (Bauger 1995) is used. Volume functions for pine (Brantseg 1967) are used for all other coniferous trees and volume functions for birch (Braastad 1966) are used for all broadleaved species. For h-trees, tree volumes are additionally predicted using dbh and measured tree height. From the two volume predictions for h-trees, correction factors are calculated per sample plot and tree species group (spruce, pine, deciduous) as the ratio of the sum of tree volumes predicted using dbh and measured height and the sum of volumes predicted using dbh and approximated height. Each single tree volume is hereby inversely weighted with its selection probability. If no trees with height measurements are available for a tree-species group on a sample plot, average correction factors given maturity class, site index class, tree species, and sampling region are used. Finally, the tree volume predicted for trees with no height measurements are multiplied by the correction factor. For h-trees, volumes are predicted using dbh and measured tree height. The heights of trees without height measurements are predicted by solving the volume function for height and using the predicted volume and dbh as input variables. Adjustments are made for breakages of stem parts with a diameters ≥ 10 cm. Above and below-ground biomass are predicted using single-tree allometric regression models for spruce and pine (Marklund 1988, Petersson and Ståhl 2006), and birch (Smith et al. 2014, Smith et al. 2016)

5.2.1.2 Increment, mortality and harvest

The volume increment calculation is based on repeated diameter measurements. The first step is to calculate the number of growth seasons between the measurements. Based on the dates of measurements and assuming a growth period of 100 days, the number of growth seasons is between 4.00 and 6.00 in a 5-year inventory cycle. The difference between the current and previous dbh is divided by the number of growing seasons to get a dbh one year before the current. For ingrown trees or in case of establishing a new plot, the annual dbh differences are predicted from the average dbh of trees of the same tree species, diameter class, two maturity class groups, and site index. The next step is to predict a volume one year before the current measurement. Assuming the same diameter-height relationship as in the previous inventory cycle (see section before), a volume is predicted with the predicted dbh. Finally, the annual volume increment is the difference between the current volume and volume one year before.

For all trees ≥ 5 cm, survival status (dead or alive) is recorded in addition to their polar coordinates and dbh. The likely cause is recorded for broken or removed trees. The volumes of dead trees still present at the plot that were alive in the previous inventory cycle are predicted in the same way as live trees. The volume of removed trees is predicted by adding 2.5 years of the previous increment to the previous volume prediction.

5.3 Stand- and landscape-level variables on 0.1 ha plots

5.3.1 Land-use and land cover

Land-use and land cover (LULC) categories fully or partly covered by a sample plot are recorded. Because they do not belong to stand-level variables, we refer to them as landscape-level variables. For non-tree covered plots that are not visited in the field, they are identified using aerial images and other map data. LULC categories are mainly required for GHG reporting and a documentation of them can be found in the latest national inventory report (Norwegian Environment Agency 2019, Chapter 6). Except for houses (as part of settlements), all LULC categories must have an area of at least 0.1 ha to be identified as an independent class. If covered by trees, measurements on the 250 m² plot are carried out on grasslands, wetlands, other lands, and some types of settlements that are accessible, but not in gardens, parks, and croplands.

5.3.2 Maturity class

The second NFI introduced a system to describe the developmental stage and the state of forest stands based on Alf Langsæter's system of five maturity classes, which modified a Swedish system

503 (Landsskogtakseringen 1938, Esmark 1965). This system was used with some adjustments until 1957,
504 when the system as we know it today was implemented (Landsskogtakseringen 1959). In productive
505 forest, the maturity class of the stand (0.1 ha) is defined based on a combination of stand age,
506 dominant tree species and site index:

507 Class 1: Forest under regeneration (age 0 yr.)

508 Class 2: Young forest (age 1-54 yrs., dependent on species and site index)

509 Class 3: Young production forest (age 15-84 yrs., dependent on species and site index)

510 Class 4: Older production forest (age 25-119 yrs., dependent on species and site index)

511 Class 5: Mature forest (minimum age 40-120 yrs., dependent on species and site index)

512

513 A further division of the maturity classes 2-5 is made to describe whether the stand is sufficiently or
514 poorly stocked, as defined by either the number of potential crop trees (class 2) or by basal area
515 (classes 3-5). Furthermore, in stands with some scattered mature trees, basal area is used to
516 determine whether a stand is to be considered a poorly stocked mature stand (class 5) or under
517 regeneration (class 1).

518 5.3.3 Stand age

519 Upon establishment of a permanent plot, stand age is determined from increment cores taken on
520 one or more representative trees just outside the 250 m²-plot. The biological age, rather than
521 chronological age, is recorded, by reducing for years of suppression below canopy after germination.
522 Alternatively, the number of branch whorls is counted in young forest where this is possible. In
523 forests that consist of either one or more than two layers, age is the basal-area weighted age of all
524 trees. In two-layered forests, age is the basal-area weighted age of all trees in the overstory.
525 Updates in subsequent inventory cycles are typically made by increasing the previously recorded
526 stand age by another five years unless the stand has been harvested since the previous
527 measurement. A new independent assessment must nonetheless be made in each inventory cycle by
528 the field staff. The new assessment may sometimes require a correction, e.g. if the stand has
529 experienced substantial mortality or has been subject to harvests. The time series on stand age
530 documents a clear trend towards and increased proportion of forest in the older age classes since
531 the permanent plots were established (Figure 5).

532

533 *Figure 5. Distribution of productive forest area beneath the coniferous limit, by forest types and age classes for periods*
 534 *1986-1993 and 2014-2018.*

535 5.3.4 Site index

536 Since the 5th inventory, the H40-system (Tveite 1977, Tveite and Braastad 1981) is adopted, using
 537 dominant tree height at a base age of 40 years in breast height as the site index value. The measured
 538 site index is recorded as a class variable, using incremental steps of 3 m range where e.g. site index
 539 14 corresponds to a dominant height between 12.5 and 15.5 m at 40 years breast height age. In
 540 cases of heterogenous soil conditions, i.e. where parts of the 0.1 ha plot area differ in productivity
 541 compared with the measured value, a subjective correction is made by the surveyor.

542 5.4 Deadwood measurements along 18 m line transects

543 During 1994-1998, downed deadwood was measured for the first time by assessing the full 250 m²
 544 plot. In subsequent inventories the supply of new dead trees was recorded. Since 2010, the standing
 545 and downed deadwood volume is estimated using line intersect sampling (De Vries 1986, Chapter
 546 13). In addition to decay status, species, length, and diameters at cross, root, and top of dead trees
 547 are measured. On more than 200 plots, both assessment methods were compared, but no
 548 significant difference was found. Since the first assessment, the amount of deadwood in productive
 549 forest has considerably increased (Figure 6).

550

551 *Figure 6. Amount of dead wood with diameter >10 cm in productive forest beneath the coniferous limit, without Finnmark*
 552 *county, by forest types for periods 1994-1998 and 2014-2018.*

553

554 5.5 Assessment of key habitats on 0.2 ha plots

555 In 2003, the methodology for mapping potential woodland key habitats (Gjerde et al. 2007) was
 556 implemented in the NFI on 0.2 ha plots (Figure 4). The results serve as a reference in the
 557 prioritization among candidate key habitat areas required by certification schemes such as PEFC. To
 558 be defined as a key habitat, the area extent needs to be at least 0.2 ha and some fraction of the key
 559 habitat needs to overlap with the 0.2 ha plot area. The area extent within the plot is mapped on
 560 paper in the field and is later digitalized into polygons at the office. Table 2 lists the main key
 561 habitats, their inclusion criteria and occurrence in productive forest as recorded for the inventory
 562 period 2014-2018. In addition to the listed habitats, which require a minimum area extent of 0.2 ha
 563 for inclusion, selected topographical features (ravines, gorges, and steep rock walls) and objects
 564 (hollow deciduous trees) are included in the key habitat registrations (Viken 2018).

565
566
567

Table 2: Selected woodland key habitats recorded in the NFI since 2003, with the main criteria for defining and mapping whole or parts of the 0.2 ha plot as a habitat polygon. The rightmost column gives the occurrence of the respective habitats as of 2016 (inventory period 2014-2018).

Key habitat	Main criteria for inclusion in polygon	Occurrence in productive forest (% of area)
Standing deadwood	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ≥ 40 standing dead trees ha^{-1} with dbh ≥ 10 cm • Distance to other dead trees ≤ 15 m 	2.7
Downed deadwood	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ≥ 40 downed dead trees ha^{-1} with diameter at root end ≥ 10 cm • Distance to other downed dead trees ≤ 15 m 	17.7
Trees with nutrient-rich bark	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Occurrence of maple (<i>Acer platanoides</i> L.) or any tree species with bark lichens of the <i>lobarion</i> group • ≥ 20 trees ha^{-1} of any of the above categories (60 in West- and North Norway) • Distance to other dead trees ≤ 25 (15) m 	0.3
Trees with pendant lichens	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ≥ 100 trees ha^{-1} with at least 10 individuals/groups of pendant lichens of more than 10 cm length within 1 m^2 of the vertical tree crown area • Occurrence of trees with lichens of the species <i>Evernia divaricata</i> (L.) Ach. or <i>Usnea longissima</i> Ach. • Only assessed for the lower 5 m of the tree 	3.1
Deciduous boreal trees in late successional stage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ≥ 40 trees ha^{-1} with dbh ≥ 20 cm of any of the species <i>Populus tremula</i> L., <i>Sorbus aucuparia</i> L., <i>Alnus incana</i> L., <i>Salix caprea</i> L., <i>Prunus padus</i> L., or <i>Betula</i> spp. • Northern Norway: only aspen is considered 	1.5
Old trees	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ≥ 30 standing old trees ha^{-1} • Minimum age for spruce/pine = 150/200 yrs. • Deciduous trees are included dependent on dbh and species (minimum dbh is 30-40 cm for boreal species and 40-50 cm for noble hardwoods) • Distance to other old trees ≤ 20 m 	2.5
Luxuriant ground vegetation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nutrient-rich forms of selected vegetation types <i>sensu</i> (Larsson 2005) 	3.1

568

569 **5.6 Field work**

570 Many variables recorded in the NFI require careful work, a lot of experience, and are partially or fully
571 based on subjective estimates by the field staff. One example is stand age which is based on one or a
572 few increment core measurements and subjective estimates of the basal area by stand layers. Other
573 such examples are the estimation of bilberry and lingonberry cover, and the classification of land-
574 cover types. The latter can be challenging for example in higher elevation areas where the landscape
575 is often a rather fine-scaled matrix of productive and unproductive forest, and even with other land
576 types blended in, such as other wooded land and areas without tree cover, and often with gradual
577 transitions between the area categories. Therefore, field crews are schooled for one week before
578 every field season. At the time of writing, due to restrictions imposed by the Covid-19 situation, it is
579 going to be the first year since the establishment of permanent plots without a field course. New
580 fieldworkers are additionally schooled by an experienced supervisor for some weeks on the job, and
581 each year the field workers are visited in the field by personnel from the office. The average
582 experience of the fieldworkers is more than 10 years.

583 5.7 Quality assurance

584 In addition to the annual field course and training of fieldworkers, several other measures are taken
585 to assure the highest possible data quality. Control inventories are done most years, which means
586 that an experienced fieldworker is doing a “blind” registration of all variables on plots that have
587 been measured by another person. While the main purpose is to identify whether certain variables
588 may be understood and recorded differently by different persons, it also helps to identify systematic
589 measurement errors due to human error or erroneous use of measurement devices. In turn, this
590 may lead to a higher focus on selected variables during the subsequent field course, direct feedbacks
591 to the fieldworkers, or to changes or additions to the NFI protocol. On average, about three per cent
592 of the plots are subjected to such a control per year.

593 Data quality assurance is also aided by several logical tests in the data collection program in the field
594 computer, allowing obvious measurement or punching errors to be corrected before leaving the
595 plot. Upon the weekly transfer of data by email to the data repository, a check is also conducted by
596 office personnel to identify likely errors, which includes a check of the new versus old data from the
597 same plot. If likely errors or inconsistencies are identified at this stage, this may be communicated to
598 the field crews, allowing a correction while the actual plot is still fresh in mind. After these initial
599 routine checks, the data is stored temporarily in a separate database and later subjected to a more
600 thorough and final quality control before being merged into the NFI database.

601 6 Specialized inventories based on the NFI

602 6.1 County inventories

603 Since the establishment of permanent plots in the sixth NFI (1986-1993 Section 3.3), additional
604 temporary field plots are used to enable reliable estimates on county level approximately every 15
605 years. Until 2011, the temporary plots were concentric as in the sixth NFI in a cluster of up to 12
606 plots associated with the permanent plots. Since then, the measurement of dendrometric variables
607 is also based on 250 m² fixed area plots but the number of variables to measure is considerably
608 reduced compared to the permanent plots. Due to the production of the Forest Resource Map SR16
609 (Section 8), also the number of temporary plots was considerably reduced.

610 6.2 Inventory of protected areas

611 The environmental authorities need data on how the currently protected areas are distributed
612 among different forest types to make sound priorities among candidate areas offered for protection
613 by forest owners. Because more precise estimates were needed than could be provided using the
614 existing grid of plots (Section 5.1.1), additional permanent plots 1.5 km north and west of the
615 existing permanent plots, were established since 2012 if they were located within a forest reserve
616 (Astrup et al. 2011). A detailed report for the protected areas was published using these new data
617 (Hysten et al. 2018). As the area of protected forest is currently increasing, new plots are continuously
618 installed. Due to economic reasons, re-measurement of the plots that were established during 2012-
619 2016 is currently limited to productive forest. To allow for a direct comparison of the forest
620 conditions in reserves with other forest land, measurements follow the general NFI protocol.

621 7 NFI use cases

622 7.1 International reporting

623 NFI data are used for various international reporting requirements such as FAO’s Forest Resource
624 Assessment (MacDicken 2015) or Forest Europe. However, no other international commitment has
625 influenced the NFI design in the last 15 years more than the Climate Convention (UNFCCC) (UN
626 1992) and its Kyoto protocol. The NFI is the most important data source for the reporting in the
627 LULUCF-sector of the (Norwegian Environment Agency 2019, Chapter 6). The possibility to cover
628 areas above the coniferous forest line and Finnmark with the NFI are owed to the UNFCCC reporting
629 needs. Since the use of the NFI for reporting under the UNFCCC, other land use categories besides

630 productive have been included in the NFI and area estimates of land uses including settlements,
631 agriculture, and wetlands, and changes among them, are reported by using the NFI grid. Also new
632 variables such as the status of drainages of organic soils on all land use categories and the
633 measurement of trees outside forest, were implemented due to the reporting under the UNFCCC.

634 7.2 Ecosystem services

635 Since the 1990s, a considerable number of new variables have been included in the NFI to
636 accommodate the growing need of information about non-wood ecosystem services provided from
637 forests, including biodiversity.

638 In the early 2000s, registration of important woody browse species, such as rowan and willow, and
639 browsing intensity from wild herbivores on trees with dbh <5 cm was implemented, together with
640 the assessment of bilberry cover. These data are annually reported to the Norwegian Monitoring
641 Program for Cervids (Solberg et al. 2012) and have also recently been used to study whether the NFI
642 estimates of woody browse availability may be suitable for predicting browse availability at local
643 scales (Wam et al. 2020 submitted). Data from the bilberry cover registrations have been used to
644 develop a model applicable to predict the abundance of bilberry in Norwegian forest (Eldegard et al.
645 2019).

646 The many variables related to biodiversity and carbon accounting that have been implemented in
647 the NFI since the 1990s have proven to be useful for a variety of purposes, in some cases even within
648 a context that could not be foreseen at the time they were introduced. For example, data on
649 deadwood and bilberry cover, and key habitats with old trees (Table 2), are currently used together
650 with other indicators in the nature index for Norway (Nybø 2015), which is a framework for
651 condensed reporting on the state of the Norwegian nature. The nature index was launched in 2010
652 and is updated every five years. We believe that the NFI data related to biodiversity and other non-
653 wood ecosystem services will see even more widespread use in future, as the length of the time
654 series increases.

655 8 Current developments and the foreseeable future

656 8.1 Forecasting and additional variables

657 Providing forecasts on the future development of the Norwegian forest has been an important task
658 of the NFI, and prognosis, e.g. on sustainable yield, have been produced regularly during the past
659 decades. Earlier prognosis tools (Eid and Hobbelstad 2000) were mainly used to forecast the
660 development of timber resources given a set of assumptions on silvicultural strategies. The recent
661 years have seen a growing need for a more flexible tool that may operate at the individual-tree level
662 and accommodates also other ecosystem services such as carbon sequestration and the effects of
663 climate change. Aided by advances in software and computational resources, this need has spurred a
664 considerable effort in the development of a new open-source single-tree simulator during the last
665 years. The developed simulator, named SiTree, is written in the R language for statistical computing
666 (Clara Antón Fernández and Astrup 2019).

667 The simulator includes single-tree models for Norway and uses the soil model Yasso07 (Liski et al.
668 2005), such that also changes in soil carbon may be forecasted. Increment, mortality, and ingrowth
669 of individual trees are forecasted either by a traditional empirical model-based approach or by
670 imputation. In the latter, the future development of the focus tree is predicted by assigning the
671 information of the nearest neighbor among the measured trees in the NFI database, using predictor
672 variables from published empirical models to define the nearest neighbor tree. The simulator can
673 flexibly accommodate a set of different silvicultural management options, different harvest
674 pathways (Antón-Fernández and Astrup 2012), and changes in forest productivity due to changing
675 climatic conditions (Antón-Fernández et al. 2016). Recently, the SiTree simulator has proven to be a
676 valuable tool to analyze the effect of different climate mitigation measures in Norwegian forest

677 (Bright et al. 2020, submitted) and in establishing a forest harvest reference level for Norway
678 (Ministry of Climate and Environment 2019). Further development of the simulator will allow for
679 even better tailored and more detailed scenario analyses in the years to come.

680 The assessment of the Nature in Norway system (NiN) at the NFI plots was planned as of the field
681 season 2020. Because this variable requires major additional field work and thus further qualification
682 of the field staff, the implementation is currently postponed to 2021 due to the Covid-19 situation.
683 Moreover, an initiative from the Ministry of Food and Agriculture and the Norwegian Environment
684 Agency to elaborate on a soil sampling system may possibly lead to additions to the field protocol.
685 While this would enable better parameterization of the Yasso soil carbon model and thus improving
686 soil C estimates for Norway, it would require substantial resources for field sampling and subsequent
687 laboratory analyses. Whether funding will be available for this task is still an open question.

688 8.2 Utilization of remotely sensed data

689 Many users prefer maps over NFI statistics for administrative units because spatially-explicit
690 information is (seemingly) easier to interpret. We notice that maps provide an intuitive access to
691 data and the flexibility of aggregation for arbitrary regions. We therefore believe, the advantages of
692 providing the required maps to users weighs stronger than local systematic errors that are inevitable
693 in model-based maps. The NFI tries to satisfy these user needs with the Forest Resource Map SR16
694 (Astrup et al. 2019) which provides model-based raster maps of the most important variables in
695 16 m × 16 m resolution. Considerable research efforts towards the integration of remote sensing
696 technologies in the NFI (Rahlf et al. 2014, Rahlf et al. 2015, Rahlf et al. 2017, Schumacher et al. 2020)
697 enable its publication since 2015. As for numerous developments of the NFI before, SR16 and its
698 satellite-based precursors (Gjertsen 2007) profited from the close knowledge exchange among the
699 Nordic forest inventory community (Kangas et al. 2018) and the Nordic NFIs that provide similar
700 systems to their users (Tomppo et al. 2008, Nord-Larsen and Schumacher 2012, Nilsson et al. 2017).

701 In SR16, metrics based on image matching and airborne laser scanning data are used to fit linking
702 models for variables such as timber volume, biomass, and Lorey's height, observed at the NFI sample
703 plots. Dominant tree species are mapped using optical satellite data (Breidenbach et al. 2020) and
704 improve the maps of other variables by utilizing stratified models (Hauglin et al. 2020 in
705 preparation). The models are used to predict the variable of interest in the form of raster maps
706 where remotely-sensed data are available. That means, the raster cells are the expected values of
707 the models given the explanatory variables based on remotely sensed data. In addition to the
708 expected values, maps of prediction intervals are provided in the hope that users will appreciate the
709 information on uncertainty in the maps.

710 The SR16 maps are regularly updated for growth using linking models with updated parameter
711 estimates using current NFI data. Changes due to larger removals such as harvests are updated by
712 setting the predicted forest attributes in pixels with a Global Forest Watch change (Hansen et al.
713 2013, Rossi et al. 2019) to zero. This also provides harvested volume as a new map product. A
714 comparison of synthetic estimates of SR16 harvest volume within several municipalities in south-
715 eastern Norway with the official harvest statistics by Statistics Norway that is based on the
716 mandatory reporting of harvested timber volume (Figure 7) can also be seen as a form of validation
717 of the SR16 volume map. In the synthetic estimates of harvest volume, it is assumed that 20% of the
718 standing timber volume remains within the forest, which is based on analysis of NFI plots with
719 harvests.

2016

720

721 *Figure 7: Synthetic estimates of harvested volume assuming 80% of the standing timber volume is utilized in 2016 per*
722 *municipality based on the forest resource map SR16 vs. census statistics of harvest data by Statistics Norway (SSB) for the*
723 *same year.*

724 Owing to user requests, SR16 also provides synthetic estimates and their model-based uncertainties
725 (Breidenbach et al. 2016, Breidenbach et al. 2018) of the predicted attributes for automatedly
726 generated segments that resemble forest stands. The segmentation and a parallel update of the
727 official forest cover map (Ahlstrøm et al. 2019) is realized by NIBIO's Geomatics department that also
728 hosts SR16 as a freely available part of Norway's natural resource infrastructure map server (Kilden
729 2020).

730 The NFI utilizes the remotely-sensed data prepared for SR16 in small area estimations on the
731 municipality level (Breidenbach and Astrup 2012) which are disseminated to users by a web
732 interface. The NFI web interface is available in English and Norwegian and gives access to standard
733 NFI data as well (Breidenbach 2016-2020). Although alternative options are currently considered
734 (Magnussen et al. 2020), conservative variance estimators assuming simple random sampling are
735 still utilized in the NFI web interface.

736 Besides the further integration of remotely sensed data (Solberg et al. 2019, Puliti et al. 2020), NFI
737 researchers also work on improved tree-level assessments through terrestrial (Ducey and Astrup
738 2013, Astrup et al. 2014) or drone-based scanning techniques (Puliti et al. 2019, Puliti et al. 2020).
739 We perceive the great potential of these relatively new measurement techniques in documenting
740 the vegetation status which enables new measurements at a later stage and providing additional

741 information, for example on stem and crown shapes (e.g. Hyypä et al. 2020). However, more
742 research and development, especially with respect to all-weather capabilities and costs, will be
743 needed to make them operational under the rough operational requirements of an NFI. Many of the
744 variables assessed in the NFI will then still require the careful assessment by field workers. A general
745 tendency that can be read from the NFI development over the years is the request for more
746 information. So far, the continuous simple stage design with fixed permanent plots for the primary
747 variables has proven to be robust to the changing and increasing information requirements since its
748 implementation in the 1990s.

749 9 Declarations

750 9.1 Ethics approval and consent to participate

751 Not applicable.

752 9.2 Availability of data and materials

753 Data are available upon reasonable request and the cited repositories.

754 9.3 Competing interests

755 We state no competing interests.

756 9.4 Funding

757 This study was supported by the Norwegian Institute of Bioeconomy Research.

758 9.5 Authors' contributions

759 JB, AG, and RA conceived the idea. JB wrote the first draft. AG, GH, and RE wrote dedicated sections.

760 All authors critically reviewed the whole text.

761 9.6 Acknowledgements

762 We are grateful for comments by and discussions with Stein Tomter and the whole NFI team. We
763 would like to thank Clara Antón Fernández for input regarding the description of SiTree, Ken Olaf
764 Storaunet for input on deadwood registrations and Volkmar Timmermann for input regarding ICP
765 Forests.

766 [To be completed after review.]

767

768 10 References

769 Aamlid, D., K. Tørseth, K. Venn, A. O. Stuanes, S. Solberg, G. Hysten, N. Christophersen and E.

770 Framstad (2000). "Changes of forest health in Norwegian boreal forests during 15 years." Forest

771 Ecology and Management **127**(1-3): 103-118.

772 Ahlstrøm, A., K. Bjørkelo and K. D. Fadnes (2019). "AR5 Klassifikasjonssystem." NIBIO Bok.

773 Anon. (1914). Betänkande avgivet av kommissionen för försökstaxering av virkeskapital, tillväxt m.m.

774 av skogarna i Värmlands län. Stockholm.

775 Antón-Fernández, C. and R. Astrup (2012). "Empirical harvest models and their use in regional

776 business-as-usual scenarios of timber supply and carbon stock development." Scandinavian Journal

777 of Forest Research **27**(4): 379-392.

- 778 Antón-Fernández, C., B. Mola-Yudego, L. Dalsgaard and R. Astrup (2016). "Climate-sensitive site
779 index models for Norway." Canadian Journal of Forest Research **46**(6): 794-803.
- 780 Astrup, R., M. J. Ducey, A. Granhus, T. Ritter and N. von Lüpke (2014). "Approaches for estimating
781 stand-level volume using terrestrial laser scanning in a single-scan mode." Canadian journal of forest
782 research **44**(6): 666-676.
- 783 Astrup, R., J. Rahlf, K. Bjørkelo, M. Debella-Gilo, A.-K. Gjertsen and J. Breidenbach (2019). "Forest
784 information at multiple scales: development, evaluation and application of the Norwegian forest
785 resources map SR16." Scandinavian Journal of Forest Research **34**(6): 484-496.
- 786 Astrup, R. A., R. Eriksen, C. Antón-Fernández and A. Granhus (2011). "Skogtilstanden i verneområder
787 og vurderinger av mulighetene for intensivt overvåking gjennom Landsskogtakseringen."
788 Oppdragsrapport fra skog og landskap **19**.
- 789 Barth, A. (1916). "Norges skoger med stormskridt mot undergangen." Tidsskrift for skogbruk **24**(4):
790 123-154.
- 791 Bauger, E. (1995). Volumfunksjoner og tabeller for furu, vanlig gran og sitkagran på Vestlandet.
792 Rapport fra Skogforsk. **16**: 1-26.
- 793 Bitterlich, W. (1948). Die Winkelzahlprobe (The angle-count sample plot), Allgm. Forstu. Holzwrirts.
794 Ztg. **59**: 4-5. Forestry Abstracts.
- 795 Braastad, H. (1966). "Volume tables for birch." Meddelelser fra det Norske Skogforsoksvesen **21**(1):
796 23-&.
- 797 Brantseg, A. (1967). "Volume functions and tables for Scots pine South Norway." Meddelelser fra det
798 Norske Skogforsoksvesen **22**.
- 799 Breidenbach, J. (2016-2020). "Landsskogtakseringen - Norway's National Forest Inventory: Make
800 your own analyses." from <https://landsskog.nibio.no/>.
- 801 Breidenbach, J. and R. Astrup (2012). "Small area estimation of forest attributes in the Norwegian
802 National Forest Inventory." European Journal of Forest Research **131**(4): 1255-1267.
- 803 Breidenbach, J., S. Magnussen, J. Rahlf and R. Astrup (2018). "Unit-level and area-level small area
804 estimation under heteroscedasticity using digital aerial photogrammetry data." Remote Sensing of
805 Environment **212**: 199-211.
- 806 Breidenbach, J., R. E. McRoberts and R. Astrup (2016). "Empirical coverage of model-based variance
807 estimators for remote sensing assisted estimation of stand-level timber volume." Remote Sensing of
808 Environment **173**: 274-281.
- 809 Breidenbach, J., L. T. Waser, M. Debella-Gilo, J. Schumacher, J. Rahlf, M. Hauglin, S. Puliti and R.
810 Astrup (2020). "National mapping and estimation of forest area by dominant tree species using
811 Sentinel-2 data." arXiv preprint arXiv:2004.07503.

- 812 Bright, R., M. Allen, C. Antón-Fernández, H. Belbo, L. Dalsgaard, S. Eisner, A. Granhus, O. J. Kjønaas,
813 G. Sjøgaard and R. Astrup (2020, submitted). "Evaluating the terrestrial carbon dioxide removal
814 (tCDR) potential of large-scale aff-/reforestation and improved forest management in Norway."
815 Global Change Biology.
- 816 Bryn, A. and K. Daugstad (2001). "Summer farming in the subalpine birch forest." Man and the
817 biosphere series **27**: 307-316.
- 818 Bryn, A. and K. Potthoff (2018). "Elevational treeline and forest line dynamics in Norwegian
819 mountain areas—a review." Landscape Ecology **33**(8): 1225-1245.
- 820 Clara Antón Fernández and R. Astrup (2019). sitree: Single tree simulator. CRAN.
- 821 De Vries, P. G. (1986). Sampling theory for forest inventory: a teach-yourself course, Springer-Verlag.
- 822 Ducey, M. J. and R. Astrup (2013). "Adjusting for nondetection in forest inventories derived from
823 terrestrial laser scanning." Canadian Journal of Remote Sensing **39**(5): 410-425.
- 824 Eid, T. and A. Fitje (1993). "Variations within stands for volume, basal area, number of trees, mean
825 diameter and mean height." Communications of Skogforsk.
- 826 Eid, T. and K. Hobbestad (2000). "AVVIRK-2000: a large-scale forestry scenario model for long-term
827 investment, income and harvest analyses." Scandinavian Journal of Forest Research **15**(4): 472-482.
- 828 Eldegard, K., J. Scholten, J. N. Stokland, A. Granhus and M. Lie (2019). "The influence of stand density
829 on bilberry (*Vaccinium myrtillus* L.) cover depends on stand age, solar irradiation, and tree species
830 composition." Forest ecology and management **432**: 582-590.
- 831 Esmark, H. M. (1965). Hogstklasser. Landbrukets årbok. Skogbruk 1965. Et abonnements-
832 opplagsverk. T. Dyring. Oslo, Johan Grundt Tanum Forlag.
- 833 Esser, J. (1994). "Jordsmonn i bjørkeskog – en oversikt over Norge." NIJOS Rapp **4**.
- 834 Esser, J. (1996). "Kjemiske endringer i skogsjord på landsrepresentative overvåkingsflater etter 5-6
835 år." NIJOS Rapp **4**.
- 836 Esser, J. and Å. Nyborg (1992). "Jordsmonn i barskog-en oversikt for Norge." NIJOS Rapp **3**: 1-50.
- 837 Fitje, A. and E. Vestjordet (1978). Bestandshoydekurver og nye hoydeklasser for gran. Meddelelser
838 fra Norsk institutt for skogforskning.
- 839 Gjerde, I., M. Sætersdal and H. H. Blom (2007). "Complementary Hotspot Inventory – A method for
840 identification of important areas for biodiversity at the forest stand level." Biological Conservation
841 **137**(4): 549-557.

- 842 Gjertsen, A. K. (2007). "Accuracy of forest mapping based on Landsat TM data and a kNN-based
843 method." Remote Sensing of Environment **110**(4): 420-430.
- 844 Haglöf, A. (2002). "Users guide Vertex III and Transponder T3." Långsele, Sweden: Haglöf Sweden,
845 AB.
- 846 Hansen, M. C., P. V. Potapov, R. Moore, M. Hancher, S. A. Turubanova, A. Tyukavina, D. Thau, S.
847 Stehman, S. J. Goetz and T. R. Loveland (2013). "High-resolution global maps of 21st-century forest
848 cover change." science **342**(6160): 850-853.
- 849 Hauglin, M., J. Rahlf, R. Astrup, J. Schumacher and J. Breidenbach (2020 in preparation). "The
850 Norwegian forest resource map SR16: Mapping forest attributes using heterogeneous sets of
851 airborne laser scanning and National Forest Inventory data."
- 852 Helland, A. (1894). Skogenes fordeling inden elvenes nedslagsdistrikter. De norske
853 flødningsvassdrag: 216.
- 854 Hysten, G., A. Granhus and R. Eriksen (2018). Arealrepresentativ overvåking av skogvernområder
855 gjennom Landsskogtakseringen.[Revidert] Rapport fra taksering utført i femårsperioden 2012-2016.
856 NIBIO Rapport. 4.
- 857 Hyypä, E., J. Hyypä, T. Hakala, A. Kukko, M. A. Wulder, J. C. White, J. Pyörälä, X. Yu, Y. Wang and J.-
858 P. Virtanen (2020). "Under-canopy UAV laser scanning for accurate forest field measurements."
859 ISPRS Journal of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing **164**: 41-60.
- 860 ICP Forest (2016). Manual on methods and criteria for harmonized sampling, assessment, monitoring
861 and analysis of the effects of air pollution on forests. Eberswalde, Germany, UNECE ICP Forests
862 Programme Co-ordinating Centre. Thünen Institute of Forest Ecosystems.
- 863 Ilvessalo, Y. (1927). "Suomen metsät. Tulokset vuosina 1921-1924 suoritetusta valtakunnan metsien
864 arvioimisesta."
- 865 Jonson, T. (1910). "Taxaloriska undersökningar om skogsträdens form." Skogsvårdsföreningens
866 tidskrift.
- 867 Jonson, T. (1915). Massatabeller för träduppskattning utgifna, Zetterlund & Thelanders boktryckeri-
868 aktiebolag.
- 869 Kangas, A., R. Astrup, J. Breidenbach, J. Fridman, T. Gobakken, K. T. Korhonen, M. Maltamo, M.
870 Nilsson, T. Nord-Larsen and E. Næsset (2018). "Remote sensing and forest inventories in Nordic
871 countries—roadmap for the future." Scandinavian Journal of Forest Research **33**(4): 397-412.
- 872 Kilden. (2020). "Skogressurskart SR16 - treslag [Forestresource map SR16 - tree species]." Retrieved
873 7 April 2020, from
874 [https://kilden.nibio.no/?lang=nb&topic=arealinformasjon&X=7117512.62&Y=315674.87&zoom=2&
875 bgLayer=graatone_cache&catalogNodes=102,402,869&layers=skogressurs_treslag_beta&layers_opa
876 city=0.75.](https://kilden.nibio.no/?lang=nb&topic=arealinformasjon&X=7117512.62&Y=315674.87&zoom=2&bgLayer=graatone_cache&catalogNodes=102,402,869&layers=skogressurs_treslag_beta&layers_opacity=0.75)

- 877 Kleinn, C., Gerald Kändler, Heino Polley, Thomas Riedel and F. Schmitz (2020 in press). "The National
878 Forest Inventory in Germany: Responding to Forest Related Information Needs " AFJZ.
- 879 Kleinn, C. and S. Tomter (1993). "The Norwegian national forest inventory." Forstarchiv (Germany).
- 880 Landsskogtakseringen (1920). Taksering av Norges skoger utført av Landsskogtakseringen - 1. Østfold
881 fylke Hamar.
- 882 Landsskogtakseringen (1933). Taksering av Norges skoger utført av Landsskogtakseringen. Oslo.
- 883 Landsskogtakseringen (1938). Taksering av Norges skoger utført av Landsskogtakseringen. Østfold
884 fylke. Revisjonstaksering 1937. Oslo.
- 885 Landsskogtakseringen (1959). Taksering av Norges skoger utført av Landsskogtakseringen. Østfold og
886 Akershus fylke. Revisjonstaksering 1957. Oslo.
- 887 Landsskogtakseringen (1968). The National Forest Survey of Norway -- Instructions for field work.
888 Oslo, Landsskogtakseringen.
- 889 Landsskogtakseringen (1970). Taksering av Norges skoger. Landsskogtakseringen 50 år. 1919-1969.
890 Oslo.
- 891 Langsæter, A. (1926). "Om beregning av middelfeilen ved regelmessige linjetaksering." Meddelelser
892 fra det norske Skogforsøksvesen 2(7): 5-47.
- 893 Langsaeter, A. (1932). "Nøiaktigheten ved linjetaksering av skog, I Bestemmelse av treantall og
894 dimensjonsfordeling." Meddelelser fra det norske Skogforsøksvesen 4: 431-563.
- 895 Langsaeter, A. (1934). "Nøiaktigheten ved linjetaksering av skog, II Bestemmelse av høide og
896 årringbredde." Meddelelser fra det norske Skogforsøksvesen 5: 405-448.
- 897 Larsson, J. Y. (2005). "Veiledning i bestemmelse av vegetasjonstyper i skog. Ny utgave 2005." NIJOS
898 håndbok 1.
- 899 Lindeberg, J. W. (1924). Über die Berechnung des Mittelfehlers des Resultates einer Linientaxierung.
900 Helsinki, Acta Forestalis Fennica.
- 901 Liski, J., T. Palosuo, M. Peltoniemi and R. Sievänen (2005). "Carbon and decomposition model Yasso
902 for forest soils." Ecological modelling 189(1-2): 168-182.
- 903 MacDicken, K. G. (2015). "Global forest resources assessment 2015: what, why and how?" Forest
904 Ecology and Management 352: 3-8.
- 905 Magnussen, S., R. E. McRoberts, J. Breidenbach, T. Nord-Larsen, G. Ståhl, L. Fehrmann and S. Schnell
906 (2020). "Comparison of estimators of variance for forest inventories with systematic sampling-
907 results from artificial populations." Forest Ecosystems 7: 1-19.

- 908 Marklund, L. (1988). Biomassafunktioner för tall, gran och björk i Sverige (Biomass functions for pine,
909 spruce and birch in Sweden), Department of Forest Survey. Umeå: Swedish University of Agricultural
910 Sciences. **45**: 73.
- 911 Ministry of Climate and Environment (2019). National forestry accounting plan for Norway for the
912 first commitment period 2021-2025.: 37.
- 913 Näslund, M. (1930). "Om medelfelets beräkning vid linjetaxering." On computing the standard error
914 in line-survey). Svenska SkogsvFör. Tidskr **28**: 309-342.
- 915 Nilsson, M., K. Nordkvist, J. Jonzén, N. Lindgren, P. Axensten, J. Wallerman, M. Egberth, S. Larsson, L.
916 Nilsson and J. Eriksson (2017). "A nationwide forest attribute map of Sweden predicted using
917 airborne laser scanning data and field data from the National Forest Inventory." Remote Sensing of
918 Environment **194**: 447-454.
- 919 Nord-Larsen, T. and J. Schumacher (2012). "Estimation of forest resources from a country wide laser
920 scanning survey and national forest inventory data." Remote Sensing of Environment **119**: 148-157.
- 921 Nordli, Ø., F.-E. Wielgolaski, A. K. Bakken, S. H. Hjeltnes, F. Måge, A. Sivle and O. Skre (2008).
922 "Regional trends for bud burst and flowering of woody plants in Norway as related to climate
923 change." International Journal of Biometeorology **52**(7): 625-639.
- 924 Norwegian Environment Agency (2019). Greenhouse Gas Emissions 1990-2017, National Inventory
925 Report, Norwegian Environment Agency. **M-1271**.
- 926 Nybø, S., Ed. (2015). Beskrivelse av hoved-økosystemene og deres referansetilstand. . Naturindeks
927 for Norge, NINA.
- 928 Øyen, K. (2006). Kartlegginga av Noregs grønne gull: saga om Landsskogtakseringa,
929 Jordregisterinstituttet og Norsk institutt for jord- og skogkartlegging frå 1919 til 2006. Ås, NIJOS.
- 930 Petersson, H. and G. Ståhl (2006). "Functions for below-ground biomass of Pinus sylvestris, Picea
931 abies, Betula pendula and Betula pubescens in Sweden." Scandinavian Journal of Forest Research
932 **21**(S7): 84-93.
- 933 Polley, H. (2020). Email subject: Legal basis for NFI. European National Forest Inventory Network
934 email list.
- 935 Puliti, S., J. Breidenbach and R. Astrup (2020). "Estimation of Forest Growing Stock Volume with UAV
936 Laser Scanning Data: Can It Be Done without Field Data?" Remote Sensing **12**(8): 1245.
- 937 Puliti, S., M. Hauglin, J. Breidenbach, P. Montesano, C. Neigh, J. Rahlf, S. Solberg, T. Klingenberg and
938 R. Astrup (2020). "Modelling above-ground biomass stock over Norway using national forest
939 inventory data with ArcticDEM and Sentinel-2 data." Remote Sensing of Environment **236**: 111501.
- 940 Puliti, S., S. Solberg and A. Granhus (2019). "Use of uav photogrammetric data for estimation of
941 biophysical properties in forest stands under regeneration." Remote Sensing **11**(3): 233.

- 942 Rahlf, J., J. Breidenbach, S. Solberg and R. Astrup (2015). "Forest parameter prediction using an
943 image-based point cloud: A comparison of semi-ITC with ABA." Forests **6**(11): 4059-4071.
- 944 Rahlf, J., J. Breidenbach, S. Solberg, E. Næsset and R. Astrup (2014). "Comparison of four types of 3D
945 data for timber volume estimation." Remote Sensing of Environment **155**: 325-333.
- 946 Rahlf, J., J. Breidenbach, S. Solberg, E. Næsset and R. Astrup (2017). "Digital aerial photogrammetry
947 can efficiently support large-area forest inventories in Norway." Forestry: An International Journal of
948 Forest Research **90**(5): 710-718.
- 949 Rossi, F., J. Breidenbach, S. Puliti, R. Astrup and B. Talbot (2019). "Assessing Harvested Sites in a
950 Forested Boreal Mountain Catchment through Global Forest Watch." Remote Sensing **11**(5): 543.
- 951 Schumacher, J., M. Hauglin, R. Astrup and J. Breidenbach (2020). "Mapping forest age using National
952 Forest Inventory, airborne laser scanning, and Sentinel-2 data." arXiv preprint arXiv:2004.13427.
- 953 Skogkommisjonen (1874). "Indstilling med foreløbigt Udkast til Lov om Skovvæsenet fra Den ved
954 Kongelig Resolution af 28de Marts nedsatte Kommisjon til Behandling af Skovlovgivningen. ." 214
- 955 Smith, A., A. Granhus and R. Astrup (2016). "Functions for estimating belowground and whole tree
956 biomass of birch in Norway." Scandinavian Journal of Forest Research **31**(6): 568-582.
- 957 Smith, A., A. Granhus, R. Astrup, O. M. Bollandsås and H. Petersson (2014). "Functions for estimating
958 aboveground biomass of birch in Norway." Scandinavian journal of forest research **29**(6): 565-578.
- 959 Solberg, E. J., O. Strand, V. Veiberg, R. Andersen, M. Heim, C. M. Rolandsen, R. Langvatn, F.
960 Holmstrøm, M. I. Solem and R. Eriksen (2012). "Hjortevilt 1991-2011. Oppsummeringsrapport fra
961 Overvåkingsprogrammet for Hjortevilt." NINA rapport.
- 962 Solberg, S., K. Andreassen, N. Clarke, K. Tørseth, O. E. Tveito, G. H. Strand and S. Tomter (2004). "The
963 possible influence of nitrogen and acid deposition on forest growth in Norway." Forest Ecology and
964 Management **192**(2-3): 241-249.
- 965 Solberg, S., H. Kvaalen and S. Puliti (2019). "Age-independent site index mapping with repeated
966 single-tree airborne laser scanning." Scandinavian Journal of Forest Research: 1-8.
- 967 Strand, L. (1994). Kilde til kunnskap. Landsskogtakseringen 75 år, NIJOS, Ås.
- 968 Thorell, K. and E. Ostlin (1931). "The national forest survey of Sweden." Journal of Forestry **29**(4):
969 585-591.
- 970 Tomppo, E., T. Gschwantner, M. Lawrence, R. E. McRoberts, K. Gabler, K. Schadauer, C. Vidal, A.
971 Lanz, G. Ståhl and E. Cienciala (2010). "National forest inventories." Pathways for Common
972 Reporting. European Science Foundation: 541-553.

- 973 Tomppo, E., R. Malimbwi, M. Katila, K. Mäkisara, H. M. Henttonen, N. Chamuya, E. Zahabu and J.
974 Otieno (2014). "A sampling design for a large area forest inventory: case Tanzania." Canadian Journal
975 of Forest Research **44**(8): 931-948.
- 976 Tomppo, E., H. Olsson, G. Ståhl, M. Nilsson, O. Hagner and M. Katila (2008). "Combining national
977 forest inventory field plots and remote sensing data for forest databases." Remote Sensing of
978 Environment **112**(5): 1982-1999.
- 979 Tomter, S. M. (2016). Norway. National forest inventories - Assessment of Wood Availability and
980 Use, Springer: 601-619.
- 981 Tomter, S. M., Ed. (2019). Landsskogtakseringen 100 År 1919–2019, Norsk institutt for bioøkonomi-
982 NIBIO.
- 983 Tomter, S. M., G. Hysten and J.-E. Nilsen (2010). Norway. National Forest Inventories: Pathways for
984 Common Reporting. E. Tomppo, T. Gschwantner, M. Lawrencel and R. E. McRoberts, European
985 Science Foundation: 411-424.
- 986 Tveite, B. (1977). "Site-index curves for Norway spruce (*Picea abies* (L.) Karst.). Norwegian Forest
987 Research Institute. Report 33: 1–84." Norwegian with English summary.
- 988 Tveite, B. and H. Braastad (1981). "Bonitering for gran, furu og bjørk." Norsk Skogbruk.
- 989 UN (1992). United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC). New York.
- 990 Vestjordet, E. (1967). Funksjoner og tabeller for kubering av stående gran (Functions and tables for
991 volume of standing trees. Norway spruce). . Meddelelser fra Det norske Skogforsøksvesen.
- 992 Vestjordet, E. (1968). "Volum av nyttbart virke hos gran og furu basert på relativ høyde og diameter i
993 brysthøyde eller ved 2,5 m fra stubbeavskjær." Meddr norske SkogforsVes **25**: 411-459.
- 994 Vidal, C., I. Alberdi, L. Hernández and J. Redmond (2016). National forest inventories - Assessment of
995 Wood Availability and Use, Springer.
- 996 Viken, K. O. (2018). Landsskogtakseringens feltinstruks 2018.
- 997 Wam, H. K., E. J. Solberg, R. Eriksen and A. Granhus (2020 submitted). "Monitoring food for large
998 herbivores in forests: associations and discrepancies between National Forest Inventory and local
999 inventories." Ecological Indicators.
- 1000